

WAYS OF EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF INVESTMENT STRATEGIES

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Abstract. In this scientific thesis, the relevance of developing investment strategies in joint-stock companies is based. The main stages of investment strategy development and its main tasks are revealed. Proposals and recommendations for ensuring financial stability by improving investment strategies in joint-stock companies have been developed.

Keywords: investment, strategy, financial stability, efficiency, risk, financial supply, savings.

In assessing the effectiveness of investment activity in joint-stock companies, the extent to which investment strategies are effectively put into practice takes an important place. We know it from the results of the research that the investment strategy is the main link of investment activity and is of great importance in ensuring financial stability in the future. Of course, in the process of research, why is it necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of an investment project and what are the methods of its implementation? we will try to answer the question. If we analyze the real situation, the question of investing in a certain project can be very difficult. A study of foreign investment decision-making practices shows that most Western companies use several methods of investment evaluation and financial decisions are made by comparing the results obtained with other efficiency ratios. The concept of efficiency of an investment project is usually expressed through its level and compliance with the goals and interests of investment participants. Several econometric instruments are used to determine this level.

The issue of determining the investment strategy in the organization of investment activities is also an issue on the agenda. Investment strategy means the long-term goals of investment activities and the system of investment approaches, as well as the selection of highly effective ways to achieve the set goals, defined in the general tasks of the development of the enterprise. The investment strategy is an effective tool for prospective management of the enterprise's investment activity and reflects the concept of enterprise development. Also, as a general plan for the implementation of investment activity, important areas of investment activity, forms of investment activity; ways of forming investment resources of the enterprise; the sequence of stages of realization of long-term investment goals of the enterprise; the limits of the possibilities of investment activity of the enterprise according to the directions and forms of investment activity; defines a system of official criteria for modeling, implementation and evaluation of investment activity. The process of developing an investment strategy includes setting the goals of the investment strategy, optimizing the composition of the investment resources and their rational distribution, developing the investment policy on the most important aspects, and ensuring mutually effective relations with the external investment environment. Investment strategy is seen as an effective tool for prospective management of the enterprise's investment activities and reflects the concept of enterprise development.

The process of developing an enterprise's investment strategy is carried out in the following stages (Fig. 1):

1-Figure. Stages of development of enterprise investment strategy ¹

The period of investment strategy formation depends on the length of the period adopted for the formation of the general strategy of the enterprise's development - the period of the investment strategy should not exceed this limit; opportunities to forecast the state of the economy and investment market - the investment strategy of large enterprises in developed countries is developed for 5-10 years; and in conditions of economic instability, it should not exceed 2-3 years on average; industry-related features of the enterprise - the period of investment strategy formation in the fields of retail trade, consumer goods production is shorter (1-3 years in developed countries); longer (4-6 years) in production of means of production, in mineral resources; We set the longest period for institutional investors (over 6 years); the scale of the enterprise.

¹ It was prepared by the author.

In large enterprises, we developed investment strategies for a relatively longer period. The formation of strategic goals, the analysis of strategic opportunities, the selection of strategic directions and forms of investment activity, as well as the determination of the strategic directions of the formation of investment resources are important stages in the development of the enterprise's investment strategy. The investment policy reflects the form of implementation of the enterprise's investment strategy at separate stages of its implementation in the section of the most important areas of investment activity. The difference between investment policy and investment strategy is formed in terms of specific activities that require effective management to achieve the main strategic goals.

In our opinion, in order to improve investment strategies, special attention should be paid to the following:

Provide regulatory indicators on important indicators that ensure the investment attractiveness of joint-stock companies. In order to assess the investment attractiveness, it is necessary to pay attention to two important aspects. The first is the investment attractiveness of investing in a certain object. In this, the economic situation of existing networks, sectors and clusters in a specific regional system is analyzed. In the implementation of the economic analysis, the basic indicators for determining the effectiveness of investment projects and programs (net discounted income, payback period, profit rate, internal rate of return) are evaluated. The second is the investment attractiveness of the economic system of joint-stock companies. For this, the analysis of the following situations is provided: the existing legal and regulatory framework, political situation, investment environment, socio-economic conditions, level of protection of investors' interests, level of taxation, and strategic and administrative resources.

Investment climate and risk levels are inversely related. The more favorable the investment environment is, the lower the investor's business risk is, and this activates the inflow of investors. On the contrary, if the investment environment is unfavorable, the level of risk is high. This leads to an increase in spending on the

part of the recipient of the investment. The state of the investment environment is important not only for the investor but also for the recipient of the investment.

Financial managers have a great role in increasing the investment activity of joint-stock companies. Because one of the main management objects of financial management in corporate structures is the investment activity of the enterprise. In the implementation of investment activities in joint-stock companies, special attention is paid to the income from the investment project, its efficiency, the security of the investment project, and the liquidity of investment funds. Participation in international stock markets is the main way to attract investments in joint-stock companies. However, we know that there are a number of requirements for the listing of corporate structures in the international stock markets. Taking into account that there are very few corporate structures that fulfill such requirements in our country, in the future, it is necessary to pay special attention to the issue of ensuring equal participation in the international capital market by large joint-stock companies and attracting financial resources from the stock market.

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